

Relationship between Talent and Conflict Management: Staff Nurses' Perspective

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Abstract: **Background:** Talent management ensures that the right staff nurses' with the best professional capabilities are in the correct positions in the work environment. Additionally, talent management focuses on providing chances for staff nurses' development and expanding their cognitive capacity that leads to reducing conflict and overcoming all problems by using appropriate skills to manage the conflict. **Aim:** To investigate the relationship between talent and conflict management among staff nurses. **Study design:** A descriptive correlational research design was utilized to conduct this study. **Setting:** All inpatient care units in Shoubrakhet General Hospital. **Subjects:** Convenience sampling from staff nurses (n=280) who were working in the previously selected settings and available during the time of data collection distributed as follows; staff nurse with bachelor's degree, staff nurse with technical nursing institute, and staff nurse with secondary nursing school diploma. **Tools:** Two tools were used in order to conduct this study: Talent management questionnaire and Rahim Organizational Conflict Inventory-II (ROCI-II). **Results:** The finding of this study revealed that the highest mean percent score of talent management as perceived by studied staff nurses was related to talent development dimension, while the highest mean score of conflict management skills as perceived by the studied staff nurses was related to integrating style. **Conclusion:** The finding of this study concluded that there was no statistically significant correlation between total talent management and total conflict management skills ($r = 0.113$, $p = 0.060$). **Recommendations:** Conduct frequent training programs and a series of workshops on talent and conflict management skills. Also, enhance a healthy work environment and open communication with their managers, which leads to a decrease conflict and problems in the work environment. Additionally, integrate the concept of talent into the undergraduate and postgraduate curriculum to raise the awareness of future staff nurses.

Keywords: Talent, Talent management, conflict management skills.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources management is getting to be more essential due to its influence on healthcare organization advance towards accomplishing its planned objectives and goals by encouraging a positive environment between staff nurses, ongoing progress and advancement, as well as assigning the proper work for the proper individual. This can be done by talent management strategies. ^(1,2) Talent management is defined as the planned employment, assessment, development, obligation, retaining, and positioning of those individuals who have high skills that create important value to an organization. ⁽¹⁾ Talent management is essential in nursing profession. It is effective in the progress and the advancement of staff nurses. It can make competitive edge for employing, maintaining and advancing talented staff nurses. ⁽³⁾

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Further, it expands the capacity of staff nurses for growth and development, reduce the job conflict and turnover, as well as improve their engagement and quality of health care services.⁽⁴⁾ According to, El Nakhla (2013)⁽⁵⁾ talent management strategies were classified into three dimensions; talent attraction, talent development, talent retention. Firstly, talent attraction, is considered to be a technique that is applied by health care organizations to ensure that they attract and recruit talented staff nurses of high quality. Secondly, talent development refers to learning activities designed to improve the performance and updating staff nurses' skills in order to meet the requirements of continuously changing environment. Thirdly, talent retention is an attempt in which staff nurses are encouraged to stay in the health care organization for life or extreme period of time.

Talent management focuses on providing a lot of opportunities for staff nurses' development and expands their cognitive capacity that leads to reduce the conflict and overcome all problems by using appropriate skills to manage the conflict.^(6,7) Conflict management is defined as several styles, methods and procedures that are required to deal with conflicts in the working environment.⁽⁸⁾ Conflict management is the procedures to control the negative parts of the conflict on the same time with rising the positive parts of it.⁽⁹⁾ It does not refer to the conflict that will be established or handled well but it will be seen as a method on how to decrease and control the conflict.⁽⁸⁾

Conflict management is very important for health care organizational effectiveness and efficiency. Staff nurses who are efficiently managing conflict, provide a quiet atmosphere that motivates personal growth and ensures high quality of patient care.⁽¹⁰⁾ If the conflict is managed well, this leads to positive results such as creativity, staff development, as well as the presence of comfortable and safe climates in health care organization.⁽¹¹⁾ Alshammari et al., (2017)⁽¹²⁾ classified conflict into four levels: intrapersonal, interpersonal, intragroup, and intergroup. Firstly, Intrapersonal which occurs within the person. Secondly, Interpersonal that occurs between two or more nurses' whose goals, objectives, values and beliefs are considered to be incompatible. Thirdly, Intragroup which occurs between nurses within a unit or department. Fourthly, Intergroup that occurs between two or more groups in different departments or units.

Rahim (2011)⁽¹³⁾ classified conflict management into five styles as follows: integrating, obliging, avoiding, dominating, and compromising. Integrating style refers to an attempt to create a solution to meet the needs of both persons. Obliging style refers to ignoring persons own needs to meet the desires of the others. Avoiding style is expressed in a passive leaving or an active suppression of the problem in a conflict situation. Dominating style occurs when one person attempts to satisfy her/his own needs without taking into account the needs of the other persons. Compromising style refers to replace the allowances between persons in order to reach an acceptable solution that only partially satisfies them.

Significance of study:

Talent management and conflict management is considered as a new administrative priority in managing staff nurses, and contributes to about 80% of the health care organizational success.⁽¹⁴⁾ In this respect, Johansen (2010)⁽⁷⁾ stated that without talent management and conflict management, the conflicts and problems will increase with high turnover rate due to lack of commitment, decrease staff nurses' morale, engagement, and nurses' performance and quality of care. Furthermore, Abd Elaal and Hassan (2018)⁽⁹⁾ they confirmed that waste of a lot of energy and time, call up tension and stress which reduces productivity, creativity and consequently failure to achieve the health care organizational goals. Additionally, El Nakhla (2013)⁽⁵⁾ the level of talent management is 63%, and this level need more improvement especially in the field of talent development.

Aim of the study:

This study aims to investigate the relationship between talent and conflict management among staff nurses in Shubrakhit General Hospital.

Research question:

What is the relationship between talent and conflict management among staff nurses in Shubrakhit General Hospital?

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II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

I-Materials Research design:

A descriptive correlational research design was utilized to conduct this study.

Setting: This study was conducted at all inpatient units in Shubrakhit General Hospital.

Subjects:

The subject of this study included all staff nurses who were working in the previously mentioned setting with experience more than six months and who were available at the time of data collection and willing to participate in this study. They were divided as follow; staff nurse with bachelor in nursing science degree (n=48), staff nurse with technical institute of nursing diploma (n= 83), and staff nurse with secondary school of nursing diploma(n= 149).

Tools: Two tools were used to conduct this study:

Tool (I): Talent management questionnaire:

It was developed by El Nakhla (2013) ⁽⁵⁾. It was adapted by the researcher to examine nurses' perceptions about talent management in the workplace. It consists of 31 items divided into three main dimensions, as following: talent attraction (10-item), talent development (10- item), and talent retention (11-item). Responses were measured on 5-Point Likert Scale range from 5 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree). The overall scoring was ranging from 31-155. It was categorized into three categories as follows; low score of staff nurses' talent management was ranging from 31 to 92, medium score of staff nurse' talent management was ranging from 93 to 123, and high score of staff nurses' talent management was ranging from 124 to 155.

Tool(II): Rahim Organizational Conflict Inventory-II (ROCI-II)

It was developed by Rahim (2011) ⁽¹³⁾ to assess the behavior of staff nurses in conflict situations. It consists of 28 items divided into five main dimensions, as follows: integrating style (7- item), obliging style (6- item), avoiding style (6- item), dominating style (5- item), and compromising style (4- item). Responses were measured on 5-Point Likert Scale range from 5 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree). The overall scoring was ranging from 28-140. It was categorized into three categories as follows; low score of conflict management skills was ranging from 28 to 83, medium score of conflict management skills was ranging from 84 to 111, and high score of conflict management skills was ranging from 112 to 140.

In addition, staff nurses' demographic and work related characteristics data sheet was developed by the researcher to collect data from staff nurses. It included data such as: age, educational qualification, years of experience in nursing, and current working unit.

II Methods

1- An official permission was obtained from the Dean of Faculty of Nursing, Damanhour University and the hospital administrators of the study settings to collect the necessary data.

2- The two tools were translated into Arabic and tested for its content validity and translation by five experts in the field of study from the faculty of nursing Alexandria and Damanhour university. (Two assistant professor from the nursing administration department Alexandria University, and two assistant professor and one lecturer from the nursing administration department Damanhour University). Accordingly, the necessary modifications were done based on their opinions.

3-The two tools were tested for their reliability by using cronbach's alpha co-efficient test. The two tools were proved to be reliable where $r = 0.970$ for the tool I (talent management questionnaire) and $r = 0.880$ for the tool II (Rahim Organizational Conflict Inventory).

4- A pilot study was carried out on 10 % (n=28)of total staff nurses rather than study subjects; in order to check and ensure the clarity of the tools, applicability, feasibility, identify obstacles and problems that may be encountered during data collection, then the necessary modifications were done.

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5- Data collection:

- Data collection for this study was conducted by the researcher through a self-administered questionnaires. They were hand-delivered to the study subjects in their work settings after explaining the aim of the study.
- The questionnaires were completed in the presence of the researcher to ensure the objectivity of staff nurses' responses, non-contamination of their opinions, and to check that all items were answered. All questions were answered and explanations were given accordingly.
- Answering the questionnaire took approximately from 15-20 minutes. Data collection took a period of three months starting from August 2021 to November 2021.

6- Ethical Considerations:

- A research approval was obtained from Ethical Committee at Faculty of Nursing Damanshour University.
- An informed written consent was obtained from the study subjects after explaining the aim of the study.
- Anonymity of the study subjects was maintained.
- Confidentiality of the data collected was maintained and assured in the study.
- Privacy and the right to refuse to participate or withdraw from the study at any time was assured.

7- Statistical analysis:

The collected data were coded and entered in especial format to be suitable for computer feeding. Following data entry, checking and verification process were carried out in order to avoid any errors. Data were analyzed using the statistical package for social science SPSS (version 20). The following statistical analysis measures were used:

- Descriptive statistical measures, which included: numbers, percentages, and averages (Minimum, Maximum, Arithmetic mean (X), Standard deviation (SD)).
- Statistical analysis tests, which included:
 - Chi square was used to examine relationship of levels of talent management and levels of organizational conflict, and studied staff nurses' demographic and work related characteristics.
 - Student T test and F ANOVA test was used to examine relationship of means score of talent management and means score of organizational conflict and studied staff nurses' demographic and work related characteristics.
 - Pearson correlation was done to measure the degree of association between dimensions of talent management and organizational conflict.
 - Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was used done to assess reliability of the talent management questionnaire and Rahim organizational conflict inventory-II.

III. RESULTS

Table (1): Demographic and Work Related Characteristics of Staff Nurses:

Table 1 shows that 45.7 % of staff nurses were in the age group between 20-30 years old, while about 44.6 % of them were in the age group between 30-40, and only about 9.7 % were 40 years old and more. Also, the mean \pm SD of age of staff nurses were 20.96 ± 1.908 . This table also, illustrates that 17.2% of the staff nurses had bachelor degree in nursing science, while 29.6% of the staff nurses had technical institute of nursing diploma, and 53.2% of the staff nurses had secondary school of nursing diploma. Regarding the staff nurses' years of experience in nursing, 29.3% had less than 5 years of experience, while 22.1 % of them 5-10 years of experience, and slightly less than one half (48.6%) had more than 10 years of experience. 12.5% of the staff nurses were working in surgical unit, while 6.8% of them were working in communicable disease unit.

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Table (1): Distribution of Staff Nurses According to Their Demographic and Work Related Characteristics:

Nurses' characteristics	Total N=280	
	No.	%
Age (years)		
▪ 20-	128	45.7
▪ 30-	125	44.6
▪ ≥40	27	9.6
Min- Max	18.0-27.0	Mean ± SD
		20.96 ± 1.908
Level of education		
▪ Bachelor degree	48	17.1
▪ Technical Institute of Nursing Diploma	83	29.6
▪ Secondary School of Nursing Diploma	149	53.2
Years of experience		
▪ <5	82	29.3
▪ 5-	62	22.1
▪ ≥10	136	48.6
Working units		
▪ Intensive care unit	30	10.7
▪ Pediatric incubator	24	8.6
▪ Pediatric ICU	25	8.9
▪ Pediatric unit	22	7.9
▪ Medical unit	31	11.1
▪ Emergency	23	8.2
▪ Dialysis	21	7.5
▪ OR	24	8.6
▪ Communicable diseases	19	6.8
▪ Obstetric unit	26	9.3
▪ Surgical unit	35	12.5

Table (2): Mean Percent Score of Staff Nurses' Talent Management:

Table 2 illustrates that the overall score of total talent management was medium score 119.74±15.72. In addition, the highest mean percent score of talent management as perceived by staff nurses was related to talent development dimension 79.96%. On the other hand, the lowest dimension was three thirds related to talent retention (75.25%).

Table (2) Mean Percent Score of Staff Nurses' Talent Management:

Items	Min -Max	Mean ± SD	Mean Percent Score	Rank
- Talents' attraction	10.0-50.0	39.36±6.092	78.72%	2
- Talents' development	24.0-50.0	38.98±5.244	79.96%	1
- Talents' retention	14.0-55.0	41.39±5.967	75.25%	3
Total Talents' Management	50.0-155.0	119.74±15.72	77.25%	

Table (3): Mean Percent Score of Staff Nurses' Conflict Management Skills:

Table 3 shows the overall score of total conflict management skills was medium score 90.45±9.534. In addition, the mean percent score of conflict management skills as perceived by staff nurses were ordered as follows integrating, avoiding, obliging, compromising, and dominating style (79.14%, 76.47%, 65.43%, 58.45%, 34.00%) respectively.

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Table (3): Mean Percent Score of Staff Nurses’ Conflict Management Skills:

Items	Min -Max	Mean ± SD	Mean Percent Score	Rank
- Integrating style	14.0-35.0	27.70±3.565	79.14%	1
- Obliging style	6.0-30.0	19.63±4.268	65.43%	3
- Avoiding style	12.0-30.0	22.94±4.691	76.47%	2
- Dominating style	5.0-20.0	8.500±3.502	34.00%	5
- Compromising style	4.0-18.0	11.69±2.754	58.45%	4
Total Organizational Conflicts	60.0-116.0	90.45±9.534	64.61%	

Table (4): Relationship Between Mean Score of Talents’ Management as Perceived by Staff Nurses and their Demographic and Work Related Characteristics:

As evident in table 4 there were statistically significant differences between the mean score of talent management as perceived by the staff nurses and their demographic characteristics namely; age and years of experience in nursing (p value 0.000, 0.000) respectively. While, there were no statistically significant differences between the mean score of talent management as perceived by staff nurses and the two-remaining demographic characteristics namely; educational qualification and current working units (p value 0.123, 0.193) respectively.

The highest mean score of talent management as perceived by the staff nurses was found among staff nurses with 40 or more years old (127.07 ± 9.081), while the lowest mean score was found among the studied staff nurses with 20 to less than 30 years (115.61 ± 15.821). Moreover, the highest mean score was found among staff nurses with technical institute of nursing diploma (122.52 ± 14.063), while the lowest mean score was found among staff nurses with secondary school of nursing diploma (118.11 ± 16.363). In relation to years of experience in nursing, the highest mean score of talent management was found among the staff nurses with 10 or more years of experience (123.63 ± 15.181), while the lowest mean score was found among the staff nurses with less than 5 years of experience (113.17 ± 15.712). Moreover, the highest mean score was found among staff nurses were working in pediatric unit (126.45 ± 16.735), while the lowest mean score was found among staff nurses were working in emergency (114.65 ± 13.849).

Table (4): Relationship Between Mean Score of Talents’ Management as Perceived by Staff Nurses and their Demographic and Work Related Characteristics:

Nurses’ characteristics	Mean Score of Talents’ Management	Test of Significance
	Mean ± S. D	
Age (years)		
▪ 20-	115.61±15.821	F=9.694 P=0.000*
▪ 30-	122.38±15.684	
▪ ≥40	127.07±9.081	
Level of education		
▪ Bachelor degree of Ng	119.98±16.023	F=2.155 P=0.123
▪ Technical Institute of Ng	122.52±14.063	
▪ Secondary School of Ng	118.11±16.363	
Years of experience		
▪ <5	113.17±15.712	F=12.227 P=0.000*
▪ 5-	119.90±14.168	
▪ ≥10	123.63±15.181	
Current working unit		
▪ Intensive care unit	120.60±12.751	F=1.372 P=0.193
▪ Pediatric incubator	117.13±20.094	
▪ Pediatric ICU	115.72±18.756	

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▪ Pediatric unit	126.45±16.735	
▪ Medical unit	118.90±16.269	
▪ Emergency	114.65±13.849	
▪ Dialysis	115.95±17.305	
▪ OR	121.17±17.360	
▪ Communicable diseases	118.74±16.309	
▪ Obstetric unit	124.73±15.136	
▪ Surgical unit	121.66±7.0290	

F = ANOVA test * Statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Not statistically significant at $p > 0.05$

Table (5): Relationship Between Mean Score of Conflict Management Skills as Perceived by Staff Nurses and their Demographic and Work Related Characteristics:

As evident in table 5, there were statistically significant differences between the mean score of conflict management as perceived by the staff nurses and their demographic characteristics namely; educational qualification, years of experience in nursing, and current working units (p value 0.014, 0.000, 0.019) respectively. While, there was no statistically significant differences between the mean score of conflict management as perceived by staff nurses and their age (p value 0.069). The highest mean score of conflict management as perceived by the staff nurses was found among staff nurses with 40 or more years old (92.63 ± 11.89), while the lowest mean score was found among the staff nurses with 20 to less than 30 years (89.06 ± 8.123). Moreover, the highest mean score was found among staff nurses with technical institute of nursing diploma (92.71 ± 9.554), while the lowest mean score was found among staff nurses with secondary school of nursing diploma (88.97 ± 9.733).

In relation to years of experience in nursing, the highest mean score of conflict management was found among the staff nurses with 10 or more years of experience (92.89 ± 9.996), while the lowest mean score was found among the staff nurses with 5 to less than 10 years of experience (88.06 ± 9.429). Moreover, the highest mean score was found among staff nurses were working in communicable diseases (94.47 ± 9.252), while the lowest mean score was found among staff nurses were working in medical unit (84.81 ± 10.60).

Table (5): Relationship Between Mean Score of Conflict Management Skills as Perceived by Staff Nurses and their Demographic and Work Related Characteristics:

Nurses' characteristics	Mean Score of Organizational Conflicts	Test of Significance
	Mean ± S. D	
Age (years)		
▪ 20-	89.06±8.123	F=2.704 P=0.069
▪ 30-	91.39±10.17	
▪ ≥40	92.63±11.89	
Level of education		
▪ Bachelor degree of Ng	91.10±8.104	F=4.335 P=0.014*
▪ Technical Institute of Ng	92.71±9.554	
▪ Secondary School of Ng	88.97±9.733	
Years of experience		
▪ <5	88.20±7.753	F=9.197 P=0.000*
▪ 5-	88.06±9.429	
▪ ≥10	92.89±9.996	
Current working unit		
▪ Intensive care unit	90.00±8.354	F=2.184 P=0.019*
▪ Pediatric incubator	89.46±9.353	
▪ Pediatric ICU	88.92±9.626	

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▪ Pediatric unit	91.55±8.991	
▪ Medical unit	84.81±10.60	
▪ Emergency	88.39±7.316	
▪ Dialysis	92.00±5.788	
▪ OR	91.42±11.46	
▪ Communicable diseases	94.47±9.252	
▪ Obstetric unit	92.65±9.550	
▪ Surgical unit	92.83±10.06	

F = ANOVA test * Statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Not statistically significant at $p > 0.05$

Table (6): Correlation Matrix between the Dimensions of Talents' Management and Conflict Management Skills:

Table 6 reveals that there was no statistically significant and weak correlation between total talent management and total conflict management skills, where ($r = 0.113, p = 0.060$).

Table (6): Correlation Matrix between the Dimensions of Talents' Management and Conflict Management Skills:

Dimensions		Talent attraction	Talent development	Talent retention	Total talents' Management
Integrating style	R	0.093	0.159	0.120	0.135
	P	0.120	0.008*	0.044*	0.024*
Obliging style	R	0.106	0.134	0.105	0.125
	P	0.076	0.025*	0.081	0.036*
Avoiding style	R	0.065	0.053	0.057	0.064
	P	0.282	0.381	0.342	0.285
Dominating style	R	-0.055	-0.155	-0.140	-0.126
	P	0.357	0.009*	0.019*	0.034*
Compromising style	R	0.086	0.071	0.041	0.073
	P	0.152	0.236	0.493	0.226
Total Organization Conflicts	R	0.119	0.109	0.080	0.113
	P	0.047*	0.070	0.181	0.060

r = Pearson correlation * Significant p at ≤ 0.05

$r \geq 0.9$ very high correlation $r 0.7- < 0.9$ high correlation $r 0.5- < 0.7$ moderate correlation $r < 0.5$ low correlation

IV. DISCUSSION

Talent management is a comprehensive approach, a source of competitive advantage, and an essential element of human resource management. ⁽³⁾ Healthcare organizations are putting more effort into talent management processes that encourage staff nurses to be fully engaged and satisfied as well as increase staff nurses retention. ⁽¹⁵⁾ In addition, Conflict management is very important for health care organizational effectiveness and efficiency. It does not refer to the conflict that will be established or handled well, but it will be seen as a method for how to decrease and control the conflict. ⁽⁸⁾

Talent and conflict management are an essential field that focuses on developing and enhancing the abilities and skills of talented staff nurses to increase their obligation and responsibility, improve their psychological state, control conflicts and use the appropriate skills to deal with conflict, and increase their loyalty to the healthcare organization, which leads to improved job performance, enhances positive outcomes, and increases satisfaction for patients. ^(16,17) The result of this study concluded that the highest mean percent score of talent management as perceived by staff nurses was related to the talent development dimension, and the lowest dimension was related to talent retention. The result of this study was supported by Kheirkhah, Akbarpouran, Haghani (2016) ⁽¹⁸⁾ who concluded that the highest mean percent score was related to the talent development dimension. On the other hand, this result was contradict with El Nakhla (2013) ⁽⁵⁾ who revealed that the lowest mean percent score was related to the talent development dimension.

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Also, the result of this study illustrated that the highest mean percent score of conflict management skills as perceived by the staff nurses was related to integrating style and the lowest mean percent score was related to dominating style. The result of this study was supported by Alhamdan, Nussera, Masa'deh (2016)⁽¹⁹⁾ who indicated that staff nurses have the highest mean score of conflict management skills was related to integrating style. On the other hand, this result was inconsistent with Raykova, Semerdjieva, Torniyova (2020)⁽²⁰⁾ who revealed that the lowest mean percent score was related to integrating style. In addition, the result of this study indicated that there was a statistical significant difference between the overall mean score of talent management as perceived by staff nurses and their age and years of experience in nursing. This result goes in the same line with Elkady, Bassiouni, and Atalla (2019)⁽³⁾ and Maurya and Agarwal (2018)⁽²¹⁾ who concluded that there was statistical significant relationship between nurses' perceptions of talent management and their age and years of experience in nursing. Conversely, Elsaid (2017)⁽²²⁾ reported that there were no significant differences between age and talent management.

While, the result of this study concluded that there was no statistical significant differences between the overall mean score of talent management as perceived by the staff nurses and their educational qualifications and current working units. The result of this study was supported by AL-Jarrah, Abu Dawla (2015)⁽²³⁾ and Wawas, Jwaifell (2019)⁽²⁴⁾ they reported that there were no significant differences between educational qualifications and current working units, and talent management. On the other hand, this result is inconsistent with Maamari, Alameh (2016)⁽²⁵⁾ who concluded that there was statistical significant differences between educational qualifications and current working units, and talent management.

Also, the result of this study confirmed that there were statistical significant differences between the overall mean score of conflict management as perceived by the staff nurses and their educational qualifications, years of experience in nursing, and current working units. Regarding their educational qualifications, the highest mean score was found among staff nurses with a technical institute of nursing diploma. The result of this study was concluded by Abd-Elrhaman, Ghoneimy (2018)⁽²⁶⁾ who revealed that there was a positive statistical significant correlation between conflict management strategies and educational qualifications. While, this result was inconsistent with Al-Hamdan, Norries, Anthony (2014)⁽²⁷⁾ who reported that there were no statistical significant differences between conflict management strategies and educational qualifications.

As regarding to years of experience in nursing, the highest mean score of conflict management was found among the staff nurses with 10 years or more years of experience. This result of this study was consistent with Al-Hamdan, Nussera, Masa'deh (2016)⁽¹⁹⁾ who concluded that there was a statistical significant difference between years of experience and conflict management. Conversely, Baddar, Salem, Villagracia (2016)⁽²⁸⁾ who indicated that there was no statistical significant difference relation between nurses' use of conflict resolution strategies and years of nursing experience.

Related to current working units, the highest mean score was found among staff nurses working in communicable diseases, while the lowest mean score was found among staff nurses working in medical unit. The result of this study was indicated by Başoğul (2021)⁽²⁹⁾ who concluded that there was a statistical significant differences between current working units and conflict management skills. While, this result inconsistent with Al-Hamdan, Norries, Anthony (2014)⁽²⁷⁾ who reported that there were no statistical significant differences between conflict management skills and current working units.

Meanwhile, the result of this study finding showed that no statistical significant differences between the overall mean score of conflict management skills as perceived by staff nurses and their age. The highest mean score of conflict management as perceived by the staff nurses was found among staff nurses who were 40 or more years old. The result of this study was supported by Başoğul, Özgür (2016)⁽³⁰⁾ who concluded that there were no statistical significant differences between conflict management strategy and age. However, this result was inconsistent Al-Hamdan, Nussera, Masa'deh (2016)⁽¹⁹⁾ who reported that there was a statistical significant difference between conflict management strategy and age.

The result of this study showed that there was no statistical significant and weak correlation between total talent management and total conflict management skills. The explanation is parallel to the finding of Taamneh et al., (2021)⁽³¹⁾ who concluded that there were no statistical significant differences in talent management. On the contrary, these findings contradict the results of the study conducted by Hashemzaee and Ghasemi (2017)⁽³²⁾ which stated that there were statistical significant differences between talent management, job motivation, and conflict management skills.

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V. CONCLUSION

The findings of the present study revealed that there was no statistically significant and weak correlation between total talent management and total conflict management skills as perceived by the studied staff nurses. In addition, the result of this study illustrated that the highest mean percent score of talent management as perceived by the studied staff nurses was related to the talent development dimension. Also, the result of this study showed that the highest mean score of conflict management skills as perceived by the studied staff nurses was related to integrating style.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

A. The hospital administrators should:

- Review the health care organization's policies about the human resources management to maintain a competitive advantage and retain the talented staff nurses.
- Integrate the concept of talent into the undergraduate and postgraduate curriculum to raise the awareness of future staff nurses toward skills, attitudes, and abilities that are necessary to motivate an individual's self, on one hand, and to motivate others on the other hand.
- Conduct frequent training programs and a series of workshops on talent and conflict management skills for all staff nurses in their work environment.

B. The first line nurse managers should:

- Provide a supportive work environment through the availability of adequate staff members and resources to decrease workload that lead to decrease conflict and provide high quality care.
- Coordinate for a supervision process to identify needs and provide continuous and constructive feedback.
- Establish an effective performance appraisal system that help in the development and improvement of staff nurses' performance.

C. The staff nurses should:

- Attend frequent training programs, and workshops concerning talent, skills, creative behavior, career development, and conflict management skills.
- Update knowledge about conflict management skills.
- Accept individual differences and respect other's values and beliefs.

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